

ANALYSIS OF SCIENTIFIC AND HISTORICAL LITERATURE ON THE ECONOMIC LIFESTYLE, MATERIAL AND SPIRITUAL CULTURE OF THE SANGZOR–ZOMIN REGION

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Abstract. This article analyzes the scientific and historical literature devoted to the economic lifestyle, as well as the material and spiritual culture of the population of the Sangzor–Zomin region. The research traces the historiography of the region’s study from the Russian Empire period to the present day, classifying it into four stages: the imperial, Soviet, independence, and foreign research periods. Special attention is given to the works of Russian orientalists, Soviet ethnographers, and modern Uzbek scholars who have studied the ethnic composition, settlement patterns, and toponymy of the Jizzakh oasis. The paper highlights how historical, linguistic, and archaeological sources collectively contribute to understanding the ethnocultural and socioeconomic evolution of the region. Furthermore, it explores the role of foreign researchers in interpreting the history of Ustrushona and the ethnopolitical landscape of Central Asia.

Keywords: Sangzor–Zomin region, Jizzakh oasis, historiography, ethnography, ethnonymy, toponymy, Ustrushona, material and spiritual culture, ethnocultural history, Central Asia.

Introduction. The study of the Sangzor–Zomin region represents an important direction in understanding the historical and cultural development of Central Asia. This territory, located in the middle reaches of the Zarafshan oasis, has long served as a bridge between various ethnic groups, languages, and civilizations. The economic lifestyle, material, and spiritual culture of the local population have evolved under the influence of natural conditions, socio-political changes, and interethnic interactions throughout different historical periods.

Scientific research on the history of the Sangzor–Zomin region began in the late nineteenth century, primarily within the framework of Russian imperial expeditions aimed at studying the geography, ethnography, and demography of Turkestan. Later, during the Soviet period, the focus shifted toward the analysis of ethnogenesis, settlement systems, and ethnolinguistic features. Since Uzbekistan’s independence, new approaches have emerged based on archaeological findings, written sources, and ethnographic fieldwork, offering a more comprehensive view of the region’s historical and cultural processes.

This article provides a historiographical review of the main stages in the study of the Sangzor–Zomin region—from the imperial and Soviet eras to the post-independence and foreign research periods. By analyzing various scientific sources, it aims to reveal how different scholarly traditions have contributed to our understanding of the region’s economic activities, material culture, and spiritual heritage. The findings highlight the significance of the Sangzor–Zomin oasis as a unique historical and ethnocultural zone within Uzbekistan and Central Asia as a whole.

METHOD. The research is based on a comprehensive historiographical and comparative analysis of scientific sources related to the history, ethnography, and culture of the Sangzor–Zomin region. The methodological framework combines historical-descriptive, analytical, and

comparative approaches to ensure a systematic examination of both primary and secondary sources.

In the first stage, archival materials, early travel accounts, and works of Russian orientalists and ethnographers from the nineteenth century were reviewed to trace the initial stages of the region's scholarly exploration. The second stage involved the study of Soviet-era research, which provided valuable insights into the ethnogenesis, settlement structure, and cultural development of the Jizzakh oasis as part of the Zarafshan valley. The third stage analyzed modern and post-independence studies by Uzbek scholars, focusing on new archaeological findings, linguistic data, and ethnographic fieldwork that have deepened the understanding of the region's historical and cultural dynamics.

Additionally, the research employed a comparative-historical method to evaluate the interpretations of foreign scholars who investigated the history of Ustrushona and the ethnopolitical processes in Central Asia. By integrating these sources, the study identifies the evolution of academic perspectives and highlights continuity and change in the historiography of the Sangzor–Zomin region.

RESULTS. The first scientific studies on the history of the Sangzor–Zomin region began in the last quarter of the 19th century. These studies mainly focused on the oasis's natural and geographical position, location, population, cultural life, ethnic composition, and ethnotoponymy. The research was primarily carried out by Russian orientalists and ethnographers. During their visits to the Zarafshan oasis, they expressed their initial observations about the Jizzakh oasis, thereby laying the groundwork for the study of this region's history.

The historiography of the oasis's history can conditionally be divided into the following categories:

1. Historiography of the Russian Empire period;
2. Historiography of the Soviet period;
3. Historiography of the Independence period;
4. Study of the oasis history in foreign research.

Discussion.

1. Historiography of the Russian Empire Period

The first scientific studies conducted in the Jizzakh oasis were mainly aimed at exploring and utilizing the region's natural resources. These investigations were reflected in the works of Russian travelers, military officers, geographers, orientalists, historians, and other specialists. These writings provided important information on the geographical location of the oasis, the population size and ethnic composition, as well as land and water relations. This tendency became particularly evident in the numerous studies produced after the conquest of Turkestan by the Russian Empire [1].

A number of Russian researchers, in the course of their scientific exploration of the region, put forward several hypotheses. In particular, the studies conducted by A.D. Grebenkin[2], A.I. Maksheyev[3], G. Arandarenko[4], A.P. Khoroshkhin[5], M.N. Rostislavov[6], D.G. Kolokoltsov[7], A.E. Snesarev[8], and L.N. Sobolev[9] briefly discussed the population of the area, their settlement patterns, ethnic affiliation, and several place names.

The data and materials collected by representatives of the Russian Empire regarding the study of the region were regularly published in the periodical "Turkestanskiye Vedomosti". The

Russian orientalist and Turkologist V.V. Radlov, who explored the region through scientific expeditions, visited several *uyezds* of the Zarafshan oasis, particularly those within the Samarkand district, where he conducted a detailed study of the local population's ethnic composition, language, and dialectal features[10].

Among the researchers who studied the ancient history, population, and place names of Jizzakh, special mention should be made of P.I. Lerch (1867), A. Kushakevich (1870s), N.S. Likoshin (1890s), V.V. Bartold (1894), and P.S. Skvarskiy (1896)[11].

2. Historiography of the Soviet Period

During the Soviet period, researchers mainly focused on studying the ethnotoponymy of the Zarafshan oasis, considering the Jizzakh region as an integral part of this oasis and approaching their studies from that perspective. In particular, a number of studies from this period were devoted to the ancient history of the Jizzakh oasis, including the history of the ancient region of Ustrushona. These works also paid partial attention to the place names of the Jizzakh oasis[12].

The research conducted on the ancient history of the Jizzakh oasis during the Soviet era was extensive and significant. Among the first scholars to conduct a scientific study of the region's ethnotoponymy were V.V. Bartold, O.A. Sukhareva, and B.Kh. Karmysheva[13]. In addition, the works of N. Negmatov, O.I. Smirnova, V.A. Livshits, and A. Babakhanov, who explored the historical roots of the Jizzakh oasis, made substantial contributions to the study of the region's history[14].

Researchers who studied the ethnic composition of major central regions of the Zarafshan oasis—such as Bukhara, Samarkand, and the southern parts of Uzbekistan—also briefly touched upon the Jizzakh oasis and its ethnotoponymy in their studies[15]. Although V.V. Bartold did not specifically focus on the ethnic composition, ethnic history, or ethnotoponymy of the Jizzakh oasis, his articles on the history of the ancient state of Ustrushona contain valuable materials for understanding the region's past[16].

In his works, Bartold discussed the settlements of the ancient Ustrushona province, including cities, towns, and villages, as well as their geographical locations. Moreover, his studies achieved notable success in determining the localization and geography of the area. However, while acknowledging the importance of Bartold's contributions, it should also be noted that some of his conclusions were one-sided and require a more balanced reassessment in light of modern research.

A significant portion of the research devoted to studying the ethnic history of the peoples of Central Asia, particularly those of Uzbekistan, through toponymic data, was conducted after the country gained independence. It should be emphasized that during this period, researchers began to rely heavily on primary written sources in Sogdian, Turkic, Chinese, Arabic-Persian, and other languages, in combination with archaeological findings. The study of Sogdian-language documents and numismatic materials also made it possible to analyze the history of the region's peoples in greater depth. The involvement of such diverse sources in the study of local history is particularly noteworthy.

In recent decades, new interpretations of the region's history have appeared in the articles and monographs of scholars such as U. To'ychiyev, A. Qayumov, S. Qorayev, H. Hasanov, E. Murzayev, Q. Hakimov, P. G'ulomov, I. Karimov, M. Pardayev, B. To'ychiboyev, Q. Qashqirli, G'. Boboyorov, A. Zokirov, M. Mirakmalov, T. Salimov, G. Normuradova, A. Tog'ayev, A. Bababekov,

U. Alibekov, Q. Almanov, A. Pardayev, B. Mirkamilov, A. Bazarbayev, and B. O'rinboyev[17]. Among these, the research of S. Qorayev and Q. Hakimov on the toponymy of the oasis stands out for its depth, consistency, and broad scope[18].

The researchers' extensive knowledge of local toponyms and ethnotoponymy has enabled them to conduct detailed analyses of regional place names. Studies such as those by U. To'ychiyev and A. Malikov, focusing on the examination of ethnotoponyms, have provided valuable insights. Based on historical research and written sources, it has been concluded that many of the place names related to the ethnic composition of the oasis population during the late 19th and early 20th centuries originated from the developed and late medieval periods.

Research into the ethnic composition and settlement patterns of the Jizzakh oasis has shown that the inhabitants speaking Kipchak, Karluk, and Oghuz dialects lived in distinct, separate settlements. This reflects the unique sociopolitical and ethnocultural processes that took place within the oasis. The distribution of the population across the region was shaped by successive waves of migration and settlement throughout different historical periods.

Studies on the toponymic landscape of the oasis, particularly those by Q. Hakimov and B. O'rinboyev, have revealed that the region's toponymy consists of seven distinct layers. Furthermore, the works of local historians and archaeologists such as A. Gritsina, M. Pardayev, A. Raimqulov, B. To'ychiboyev, F. Maqsudov, F. Toshboyev, and O. Mamirov, who investigated the history of the oasis through archaeological sites and written sources, play an important role in clarifying the historical geography of the Jizzakh oasis. In general, these studies have placed special emphasis on exploring the ancient history of the Jizzakh region.

4. The Study of the Topic in Foreign Research

During the late 19th and early 20th centuries, there were no direct foreign studies devoted specifically to the ethnic composition of the Jizzakh oasis population or its reflection in ethnotoponymy. However, some Western scholars mentioned the settlement patterns and political roles of several leading tribes and clans that were part of the region's ethnic structure, particularly within the territories of the Bukhara Khanate (Emirate).

Foreign researchers such as Edward A. Allworth, August Nabe Samie, Yuri Bregel, and Anke von Kügelgen provided information about some of the dominant Uzbek tribes and clans — including the Yuz, Qirq, Manghit, Qong'irov, and other groups belonging to the "92 tribes" — that played a key role in the Bukhara Emirate. These tribes are also recognized as major ethnographic groups within the Jizzakh oasis, and many of the region's place names are associated with them. Another foreign scholar, Yuri Skayler, included references to specific settlements of the oasis in his research.

In addition, several foreign studies have explored the ancient history and historical toponymy of the oasis. Notably, special attention has been given to the history of Ustrushona, one of the ancient principalities encompassing the Jizzakh region. The works of French scholars such as Frantz Grenet and Étienne de la Vaissière focus on the ethnopolitical history of the Ustrushona domain and provide significant observations regarding Sogdian toponyms found within the oasis area.

CONCLUSION. The historiographical study of the Sangzor–Zomin region demonstrates the continuous scholarly interest in the economic, cultural, and ethnographic development of this unique part of Central Asia. From the earliest research conducted by Russian orientalists in the nineteenth century to the modern interdisciplinary studies of independent Uzbekistan,

the region has been examined from diverse perspectives that reflect the evolution of historical science itself.

The works of imperial and Soviet scholars laid the foundation for understanding the geography, population, and ethnotoponymy of the Jizzakh oasis, while modern and post-independence research—based on archaeological, linguistic, and ethnographic data—has expanded this knowledge and offered new interpretations. The inclusion of foreign studies, particularly those focused on Ustrushona and Sogdian toponymy, has further enriched the international understanding of the region's past.

Overall, the analysis confirms that the Sangzor–Zomin region holds a significant place in the broader historical and cultural landscape of Uzbekistan. Continued research integrating historical, archaeological, and linguistic evidence will deepen our comprehension of the region's material and spiritual culture, its ethnocultural identity, and its enduring contribution to the history of Central Asia.

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